

1974

Council on Library Resources, Inc.
eighteenth annual report

The Council on Library Resources, Inc., is a private operating foundation incorporated in the District of Columbia with the principal objective of aiding in the solution of library problems. The Council, whose Members also constitute its Board of Directors, maintains its offices in Washington, D. C.

The Council was established in 1956 at the instance of the Ford Foundation with a grant of five million dollars, to be expended over a five-year period, "for the purpose of aiding in the solution of problems of libraries generally and of research libraries in particular, conducting research in, developing and demonstrating new techniques and methods, and disseminating through any means the results thereof, and for making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and for providing leadership in and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives."

In 1960, 1967, 1971, and again in 1974 the Ford Foundation approved new grants totalling twenty-four million dollars to enable the Council to carry forward its programs of research and demonstration toward the solution of library problems.

The Council conducts its work through directly administered programs as well as grants to and contracts with other appropriate organizations or individuals. It welcomes proposals for work in furtherance of its objectives.

18th annual report

for the year ending June 30, 1974

COUNCIL
ON LIBRARY
RESOURCES,
INC.

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² Mr. Anable became consultant as of January 1, 1974.

the year 1973-74

Each annual report of the Council on Library Resources has carried grateful acknowledgement of the Ford Foundation's continuous support since 1956. This report is no exception. But special note should be taken here of the Foundation's sixth grant to the Council – \$6 million for the three-year period beginning July 1, 1974 – bringing to \$29 million the amount the Ford Foundation has dedicated to the Council's work on behalf of libraries. The grant is particularly notable since it was made at a time of financial stringency for foundations as well as other institutions. The Foundation also gave approval in principle of renewed support for three additional years beyond 1977 at a level designed principally to maintain the Council's staff and technical assistance capabilities. We believe this is a remarkable record of giving. To our knowledge, no other foundation has year after year provided the support required to develop and implement a problem-oriented program of assistance to libraries.

When the Ford Foundation established the Council in the mid-1950s, libraries were struggling to meet the needs of increasing numbers of patrons working in fields where recorded knowledge was growing at an exponential rate. The foundation funds then available to them were largely earmarked for the erection of buildings and the improvement of collections, and thus failed to attack major sources of difficulty. It was to help libraries mount an attack on these difficulties that the Council on Library Resources was created.

With the cooperation of those it was established to serve, the Council has sought solutions to some of the many problems of libraries – very often with real success. Unfortunately, the number of problems appears not to diminish; for each one solved at least two seem to rise in its place. Libraries and the services they provide are enormously important to mankind. For this reason the Council and the library community worldwide must endeavor to find additional sources of funding for the important efforts that lie ahead. Otherwise libraries will fall still further behind in the race to keep up with their users' needs.

FRED C. COLE
President

libraries and the developing technology

Almost twenty years ago, in January 1955, a prestigious group of scholars and librarians met at the Folger Shakespeare Library to discuss libraries and their problems, then reaching almost monumental proportions. They concluded, among other things, that the situation could be greatly alleviated if there existed a strong planning and development body, free to make wide-ranging attempts to seek solutions to these problems. It was in response to this recommendation that the Ford Foundation, supporter of the Folger Library conference, established the Council on Library Resources.

The Council's first annual report contained a remarkably prescient summary of the meeting by Verner Clapp, CLR's first president. In it he made two statements that laid the foundation for and continue to guide the Council's activities as it seeks feasible ways to apply developing technologies to library practices. First, Mr. Clapp said: "Perhaps the central conclusion of the [Folger] discussion was that libraries, though suffering from all the effects of the machine age, have gained disproportionately little benefit from it; that because libraries do not in many cases provide a market large enough to stimulate the supply of special equipment for their particular needs, many potentially applicable developments in science and technology have not been brought to library tasks."

"Condemned to cataloging afresh . . ."

In characterizing the changing world to which libraries would continually be required to adjust, Mr. Clapp went on to say: "In our increasingly 'one world' international uniformity acquires increasing actual and potential importance. There is an increasing amount of international interchange of information between bibliographic services, most observable (because most consciously organized) in the field of science, but important in other fields also. Meanwhile, the librarians of each country are still condemned to cataloging afresh those publications of every other country which they acquire, as though the country of origin were not already doing the job, and possibly better."

Since this statement was made, in 1957, the Council has invested large amounts of effort and money in an attempt to apply computer and

communications technologies to library work and to develop the standards that make such application possible. Mr. Clapp's comments are more pertinent than ever in today's world of increasingly interdependent bibliographic practices that have been developed to deal with the ever-growing mass of materials, both print and nonprint.

The Council has been concerned with a broad range of library problems urgently requiring solution. At one end of the spectrum, programs of international bibliographic exchange are being undertaken which force certain de facto standards on the participating national entities. These international practices themselves require formal standardization which in turn forces reexamination of national and local standards. Attempts to change national standards in order to further international compatibility run headlong into entrenched positions of nationalism, traditions of cataloging, use of language, and real problems of major investments sunk in old ways of doing business. The Council attempts to make certain that the projects it sponsors in this area are so designed as to engender international cooperation while placing the major emphasis on finding solutions to problems of national scope.

Three levels of standardization

At the other end of the spectrum lie those problems that deal in detail with the preparation of bibliographic records, especially their encoding into machine-readable form. It is now generally recognized that compatibility among bibliographic records for use in computers has three distinct component levels. These levels may be approached separately, as described below, but final compatibility among bibliographic systems will not be achieved until all three levels of standardization are reached.

Since identical internal bibliographic systems are not feasible in a democratic society, each tends to be designed to meet local needs; efforts toward compatibility among the disparate systems are concentrated instead on the communications medium used among them. For most purposes of automated bibliographic exchange, the medium is a record on magnetic tape for each bibliographic item. The first level of compatibility is achieved when the physical description of the tape and the blank record format are agreed upon. Pioneered by the work done at the Library of Congress, the blank MARC (for Machine-Readable Cataloging) format has become the U. S. national and now the international standard.

When the tape and blank format are standardized, any computer system capable of handling the tape can "read" the record. However, the bibliographic content of the data elements is meaningless to the computer unless the second level of standardization, content designation, is achieved. In the United States the wide use of the MARC rec-

ords distributed by the Library of Congress presents a de facto standard, not yet formalized, of content designation. This is a complex scheme of tags, subfield codes, and indicators that provides for almost any conceivable permutation in a bibliographic record. It has been adapted for use in many countries around the world, including the Soviet Union. Unfortunately, some systems designers fail to maintain all the detail of MARC content designation in their internal processing formats (and therefore in the records that they create locally), with the result that they cannot produce a complete MARC record which can be used in other places. This capability is, of course, vital to an effective division of labor in the creation of a truly national data base.

The third and final level of compatibility among machine-readable bibliographic records lies in the standardizing of the semantic value of the contents of each data element, no matter where the record originates. Involved here are cataloging rules, varying interpretation of these rules, rules for filing bibliographic entries in catalogs, standard and de facto standard codes used to represent bibliographic items, and the fact that traditionally each library has had a large measure of autonomy when it came to how these were all to be used locally. The wide and increasing distribution of bibliographic records from respected agencies like the Library of Congress is slowly inducing standards into record content, but a true, comprehensive standard that will make every data element in every record have exactly the same intellectual value is not for the near future. Its absolute realization is probably not possible, but it is important that everyone strive in that direction—this inevitably means surrendering some autonomy.

Bibliographic compatibility is goal

In determining what projects in library automation it will support, the Council endeavors to select those that contribute in some way to the desired goal of bibliographic compatibility and standardization, from the detailed coding of data elements for machine use to the broadest range of international cooperation. Primary focus continues to be on projects chosen for their potential to benefit all libraries, with special emphasis on academic and research libraries. Recently the Council has begun active support of several programs designed to complement each other in the construction—at the least possible cost and with a minimum of duplicative effort—of a comprehensive, authoritative, and consistent national bibliographic data base.

These and other programs dealing with national library service, automation, and networks are described in greater detail in the two sections that follow. International activity in this important area of library work is reported in the later section on international cooperation.

national library services

This is the fifth annual report of the Council on Library Resources to deal explicitly with the urgent need for national library services: central sources, governmental or private, that can make available to all libraries the services all libraries need and thereby eliminate many of the costly and time-consuming procedures that are replicated in each.¹ During the year covered by this report the nation's library community appeared to be moving closer to unity in this essential area. This was reflected by a series of articles, editorials, and reports which appeared in influential library publications early in 1974. Representative of these was the appeal in the February *American Libraries* by M.I.T. Director of Libraries Emeritus William Locke for "improved bibliographic control," with "the process coordinated by a national bibliographic center."² In the March *Wilson Library Bulletin* William J. Welsh, director of the Library of Congress Processing Department, described a "dream" network whose "national center would distribute its output of original cataloging to every regional node, which would in turn be responsible for secondary distribution."³ This period also saw the publication in the February 15 *Library Journal* of the National Commission on Libraries and Information Science's first draft of "A New National Program of Library and Information Service."⁴

The Council's concerns in this area have been demonstrated over the years through its initiation and/or support of programs like MARC, RECON (Retrospective Conversion), CIP (Cataloging in Publication), and NSDP (National Serials Data Program). These have constituted important steps along the way as the library community looked ahead to the development of national library services and national bibliographic control.

National Bibliographic Control

This year the degree of interest, climate of cooperation, and state of the art appeared to warrant a concentrated effort, and the Council increased the intensity of its investigation into the factors involved in the establishment and implementation of national bibliographic services. A most significant event in the pursuit of this goal was a three-day Washington meeting in April, jointly sponsored by the Council and the National Science Foundation. Its purpose was to attempt to provide a

¹ XIV:17-26; XV:20-25; XVI:17-25; XVII:9-13. Citations in this form refer to the Council's annual reports: for example to the *Fourteenth Annual Report*, pages 17-26, in the first instance.

² William Locke, "Do We Need a National Library?", *American Libraries* 5 (February 1974).

³ William J. Welsh, "An Old Idea in a New Setting," *Wilson Library Bulletin* 48 (March 1974).

⁴ National Commission on Libraries and Information Science, "A New National Program of Library and Information Service," *Library Journal* 99 (February 15, 1974).

solid progressive framework of approved objectives that would constitute a working program in the near term for all concerned with bibliographic control. "Bibliographic control" was defined in the background materials as "those principles and processes by which bibliographic items – books and periodicals alike – are identified to the basic level required for management of and intellectual access to information of all types." The 45 invited participants represented the various sectors of the information community involved in the activity: librarianship, abstracting and indexing, publishing, and standardization. Among their conclusions and recommendations: "We agree in principle that a requirement exists for a more coherent national bibliographic system. We further agree that a national bibliographic system will be built, but that we should not try to design it all now. We agree the programs for action which come out of this meeting should constitute some of the building blocks of the improved national bibliographic system."⁵

**On-line
national
serials
data base**

The CONSER (Conversion of Serials) Project is an attempt to create one of the "building blocks" of the improved national bibliographic system—a comprehensible bibliographic data base of serials in machine-readable form. To this end the Council had earlier encouraged and partially funded the National Serials Data Program, now an operational facility at the Library of Congress (LC).⁶ However, for a variety of reasons the NSDP evolved with a limited mission that prevented it from addressing many of the immediate needs of the library community. Even when one added the output of the MARC Distribution Service of the Library of Congress, which began sending out serials records last year, it was apparent that these activities could not build a national serials data base fast enough to satisfy requirements, especially as to retrospective records.

The gap between supply and demand was underscored by the formation of the Ad Hoc Discussion Group on Serials, composed of representatives of libraries and library systems in this country and Canada, whose purpose was cooperatively to create the desired data base.⁷ The group soon became aware of the need for a more formal structure and—with the concurrence of the Association of Research Libraries, the Library of Congress, and the National Library of Canada—asked the Council on Library Resources to assume an interim management and funding role in the development of CONSER.⁸

An initial group of participants, selected for their degree of commitment and bibliographic excellence, have been invited to pool their best efforts to build a large comprehensive data base of records on

⁵ Lawrence G. Livingston, "National Bibliographic Control; A Challenge," *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* 33 (June 21, 1974).

⁶ XII:14-15; XVI:20-21; XVII:10.

⁷ Richard Anable, "The Ad Hoc Discussion Group on Serials Data Bases: Its' History, Current Position, and Future," *Journal of Library Automation* 6 (December 1973).

⁸ Lawrence G. Livingston, "A Composite Effort to Build an On-Line National Serials Data Base," *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* 33 (February 1, 1974).

serials publications held in the U. S. and Canada. The data base will contain discontinued publications as well as currently published materials in order to meet the requirements of union lists and most serials catalogs. All work is to be based on the *Anglo-American Cataloging Rules* and on *Guidelines for ISDS* (International Serials Data System). As it becomes possible, the Library of Congress and the National Library of Canada will authenticate the contributed records against official catalogs. They will also be responsible for the continued growth and maintenance of the data base at the conclusion of CONSER and for distribution of the records during the life of the project and after. It is hoped that the data base can be built at the rate of 100,000 records per year to the point where further large scale effort is no longer required.

**Bibliographic
control of
monographs**

During the past year and a half, representatives of a number of major libraries and consortia of libraries using the Library of Congress's MARC records have been meeting at Council-initiated and -sponsored meetings aimed at identifying the prerequisites for implementing bibliographic data interchange.⁹ Because MARC coverage is still somewhat limited, these users have been creating their own machine-readable records. Some of these are based on Library of Congress cataloging not now available through MARC Distribution Service, some on original cataloging based on local practice. This has resulted in unnecessary duplicative effort as well as the creation of inconsistent (and therefore unexchangeable) records. As a result of the meetings, also attended by LC staff members, agreement has been reached on use of the MARC format, with some recommended modifications, in order to permit the desired exchange. Progress toward the initiation of a pilot effort has been made.¹⁰

**American
National
Standards
Institute**

As cooperative ventures and computer-based activities increase in number and scope, the need for accepted national and international standards becomes more pressing. A new Council grant to the University of North Carolina on behalf of the American National Standards Institute (ANSI) Committee Z39—the national standards committee for library work, documentation, and related publishing practices—continues a joint funding arrangement with the National Science Foundation dating back to 1966. ANSI Committee Z39 has been the dominant force for standardization in the library field in the United States for many years, and it has also been influential in the growing activity internationally.¹¹ The CLR-NSF funds cover chiefly travel expenses to allow the various subcommittees to meet for work on final drafts of proposed standards; much of the preliminary work is done by correspondence. All members serve without pay.

⁹ XVII:11.

¹⁰ Henriette Avram, "Sharing Machine-Readable Bibliographic Data: A Progress Report on a Series of Meetings Sponsored by the Council on Library Resources, Inc.," *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* 33 (January 11, 1974).

¹¹ XV:21-22; XVII:12.

**Cataloging
in
Publication**

Librarian of Congress L. Quincy Mumford called Cataloging in Publication (CIP) "a milestone in American library history" in making his final report on the program to the Council and the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH).¹² Supported from July 1, 1971, through August 15, 1973, by a \$400,000 CLR-NEH grant, CIP is now an ongoing activity of the Library of Congress, financed by appropriated federal funds for permanent staff positions and operating costs.

Many technical details had to be worked out and many difficulties overcome before the successful procedure, which enables publishers to print in their books LC cataloging information in standardized format, could be worked out. In 1958-59, with the support of the Council and the cooperation of 157 publishers, the Library of Congress had attempted CIP under the title of "cataloging in source." However, LC ended that program after it had been in operation for less than a year, citing the prevalence of errors in the cataloging and the cost to publishers and to itself as reasons for discontinuance.¹³ The errors for the most part resulted from the fact that the bibliographic information, which was produced from page proofs, had to be completed and returned to the publishers within 24 hours. The short deadline, in addition to putting tremendous pressure on the LC catalogers, made the whole process extremely expensive as well.

In 1971, after the Council had undertaken a preliminary study of the matter at the request of the Librarian of Congress, LC and cooperating publishers agreed to try again—this time working from galley rather than page proofs and thus avoiding the earlier problems of error and cost. Another change from previous procedures is in the elements provided by LC for the entry; under the present program LC furnishes author, title, bibliographic notes, subject headings, classification symbols, and International Standard Book Number. Pagination may be added easily by catalogers of the publications.

The CIP program, which is believed to save U. S. libraries hundreds of thousands of dollars annually, is an achievement in cooperation between Library of Congress catalogers and hundreds of U. S. book publishers.¹⁴

**American
library
laws**

The Council's oldest continuously active grant, made in 1962, awarded \$10,500 to the American Library Association for the publication of a third edition of *American Library Laws*. The grant stipulated that proceeds from sales were to be used for biennial supplements.¹⁵ Receipts have now also made possible publication of the 1973 fourth edition (a compilation of state and federal laws pertaining to libraries as of December 31, 1973), and it is expected that its sales will support future biennial supplements.

¹² Library of Congress, "Final Report on the Cataloging in Publication Project," (Washington: Library of Congress, December 3, 1973).

¹³ II:15-18; IV:24-25.

¹⁴ XVI:21-22; XVII:10-11.

¹⁵ VII:32; IX:38; X:16; XII:21-22.

A list of CLR national library services projects active in 1973-74 follows: (The first column shows grants approved in 1973-74; the second, payments on new grants and on grants approved in earlier years. The original amounts and dates of earlier grants that were not fully paid at the beginning of fiscal 1974 are given in brackets [] at the end of each entry.)

	Grants and Contracts	
	Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
American Library Association , for the publication of a new compilation of federal and state legislation to supplant a long obsolete second edition of <i>American Library Laws</i> , and for biennial supplements. Receipts from sales were used for a fourth edition (recently published) and will support future supplements. [\$10,500 – 1963]	\$ _____	\$ _____
Joint CLR-National Science Foundation (NSF) Conference on National Bibliographic Control (CLR-administered), matched by NSF, for April 18-20, 1974, conference in Washington, D. C.	4,275	3,304
Library of Congress , further support of the National Serials Data Program. (Supplements \$105,000 provided by the Library of Congress, National Library of Medicine, and National Agricultural Library.) [\$20,000 – 1973]	_____	_____
Library of Congress , for a continuation of the RECON project aimed at converting 85,000 (1968-69) English language monograph titles and 5,000 other selected titles to machine-readable form. [\$200,959 – 1970]	(9,579)	(4,129)
Meeting of the Steering Committee for the Ad Hoc Committee on Serials Data Bases (CLR-administered), toward expenses of eight participants of Steering Committee for September 21, 1973, meeting in Toronto.	1,184	1,184
National Bibliographic Data Base (CLR-administered), for programs leading to the development of a National Bibliographic Data Base.	60,000	15,768
National Book Committee, Inc. , to support a one-day conference in New York on the aggregate impact of present public policies on libraries and the free flow of books and periodicals. [\$5,000 – 1973]	_____	_____
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , as a matching grant to be used with NEH grant of \$200,000 to launch the Library of Congress' new program of Cataloging in Publication. [\$200,000 – 1971]	_____	(19,541)
University of North Carolina , to underwrite a portion of the expenses of the American National Standards Institute Sectional Committee Z-39 and its subcommittees as they work toward standards in library work, documentation, and related publishing activities. [\$61,275 – 1970]	_____	5,425
University of North Carolina , toward continued administrative support of the American National Standards Institute's Sectional Committee Z-39 .	14,000	_____
NATIONAL LIBRARIES TOTALS, 1973-74	\$ 69,880	\$ 2,011

automation and networks

The potential advantages to be derived from the computer are an important factor as the nation's libraries attempt to keep pace with demands in a period of unprecedented inflation—of materials and services on the one hand and costs of these and their processing on the other. To enable libraries to benefit from advances in automation was an important goal of the Council when it was created 18 years ago; it is even more central today. Because of the tremendous costs involved in putting the computer to work for libraries and in view of the limited funds and trained personnel available for the purpose, the Council has always encouraged the cooperation of libraries and related institutions and the sharing of developmental as well as operational costs.

While only two new grants were made in 1973-74 under this broad category, previously funded programs accounting for over a million dollars in Council support continued active under the monitorship of the CLR systems staff. Several additional grants dealing with automation and networks have been discussed in the preceding section on National Library Services.

Ohio College Library Center

The Ohio College Library Center (OCLC) continues to be a major force in library development. Established in 1967 to increase the availability of library resources for the educational and research programs of Ohio's colleges and universities, OCLC has grown from a membership of approximately 50 academic libraries in Ohio to 193 participating libraries in June 1974, including some public libraries and members of affiliated networks outside of Ohio. Negotiations now under way will very likely double this number within a year. At present OCLC operates a computer-based system that allows for on-line shared cataloging and related union catalog aspects. The data base thus being created contains very close to a million bibliographic records, chiefly of monographs, and catalog card production by June 1974 approached 50,000 per day. A serials cataloging system is close to implementation, and research and development are proceeding on serials control, technical processing, and circulation control systems. Plans for the future call for the development of remote catalog access, subject information retrieval, and interlibrary loan systems.

The Council and the U. S. Office of Education have provided most of the developmental funds needed by OCLC to achieve its broad goal; operating costs have been borne by the state and by OCLC members and affiliates.¹⁶ Members of the Council's systems group keep closely in touch with OCLC developments. The knowledge thus gained has been useful as CLR continues to respond to requests for assistance from institutions and networks contemplating the establishment of similar systems.

**Southeastern
Library
Network**

A case in point is the Southeastern Library Network (SOLINET). When OCLC began to give evidence of being a network facility capable of furnishing technical support to regional groups of libraries, members of the Association of Southeastern Research Libraries expressed strong interest in developing an OCLC-like activity in the Southeast. At their request a CLR staff member provided counsel as to possible organization and incorporation, network lines and equipment, headquarters location, etc. A 10-state network was incorporated as SOLINET, with 99 member libraries and many others waiting to be admitted to membership. After consideration of the alternatives, SOLINET has decided that, initially at least, it will tie in to the OCLC system rather than replicating it and producing a new entity.

Financially SOLINET appears to be on sound ground. The Mellon Foundation has made the fledgling library network a \$600,000 grant, and SOLINET members have already contributed \$280,000 in first-year membership fees. The Council's own financial commitment is for \$10,000 in partial support of a training program for librarians who will participate in the network.

**Stanford
University's
BALLOTS**

Stanford University's BALLOTS (Bibliographic Automation of Large Library Operations Using a Time-Sharing System) is now fully operational, supporting almost all technical processing at the library: selection, acquisition, cataloging, and production of cards, book pockets, and spine labels. Thus far the system has been campus-oriented, but it now shows promise for network extension beyond Stanford itself.

The research and development involved in BALLOTS have been supported by the Office of Education, the National Endowment for the Humanities, and the Council on Library Resources.¹⁷ Under a joint CLR-NEH grant five BALLOTS modules (services) have become operational. The purchase order/original cataloging module activated in November 1973 provides for the computerized production of much more than purchase orders and cataloging; it also supplies dealer reports, matched standing search notices, catalog data slips, invoice alert slips, cancellation notices, requester notices, cancel file slips, Title II slips, NPAC notices, and management reports. Two additional modules have since been implemented: nonpurchase order material receipts and automatic claim/cancel.

¹⁶ XVI:18; XVII:16-17.

¹⁷ XVI:18-19; XVII:18.

**Chicago's
Library
Data
Management
System**

An equally important large university library computer project is the University of Chicago's Library Data Management System. The system utilizes a Varian minicomputer in the library which interfaces with the university's central computer – an IBM 370/168. Initially supported by the National Science Foundation, the project received additional assistance from the Council and the National Endowment for the Humanities in 1970 in the form of a five-year grant.¹⁸ It is expected that this system, when more fully developed, could be used by a single large library or institution for a variety of data processing functions, as a central facility with remote terminals by a group of libraries, or transferred – as a system – to other institutional environments.

The sequential design approach is to permit ultimately the handling of a very high proportion of library functions through on-line, interactive terminals as well as batch processing and output where appropriate. The system is intended to provide great flexibility in the interfaces between operational software, terminal devices, data storage, central computer operating equipment and systems, and library or other applications.

The majority of the library's technical processing functions – ordering, cataloging, etc. – have been handled by computer data processing for some years. The library expects to have an on-line, remote multiterminal capability for handling circulation and certain other functions by late 1974.

**Southwestern
Library
Interstate
Cooperative
Endeavor**

The Southwestern Library Interstate Cooperative Endeavor (SLICE) office of the Southwestern Library Association is, with Council assistance, in its third year of serving its constituency of Louisiana, Texas, Arkansas, Oklahoma, New Mexico, and Arizona. Much of its effort this year has been in the area of interstate networking, and a recently completed study recommends a federal-interstate compact as perhaps the best organizational, financial, and legal structure for the purpose.¹⁹ SLICE has also been a key factor in the increased sharing of library resources, services, and expertise within the region. The six state libraries provide some of the funds needed for its support.

**Library
circulation
study**

A relatively small Council grant financed a study of the Ohio State University Libraries' circulation system that may prove of considerable significance. Using an archive file of 1.6 million book circulation transactions for 1972 and a bibliographic file of over a million titles, the investigator derived statistical data on a number of factors that are important in determining priorities for acquisition and access. Data of this degree of comprehensiveness have not heretofore been available to library directors as they make daily decisions in the face of problems rising from increasing activity and decreasing budgets.

¹⁸ XVI:19, XVII:17-18.

¹⁹ Harry S. Martin, "Legal Aspects of Establishing a Regional Interstate Library Network in the Southwest," (Dallas: Southwestern Library Association, June 1974).

A list of CLR automation and network projects active in 1973-74 follows:

Grants and Contracts
Approved Payments
(Reductions) (Refunds)

Bucknell University , to permit an experiment in which students will use already available terminals to search the entire data base of the library on-line. [\$28,000 – 1973]	\$ _____	\$ 16,250
Massachusetts Institute of Technology , to continue a program of controlled experiments within the Intrex Project aimed at establishing characteristics and specifications for future library information and retrieval systems. The final financial report has been received. [\$400,000 – 1972]	_____	50,000
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , matching funds toward a \$650,000 combined Council-NEH grant to the Stanford University Libraries to complete the basic development of the BALLOTS (Bibliographic Automation of Large Libraries On-line Time-Sharing) system and bring it to operational status. [\$325,000 – 1972]	_____	_____
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , matching funds for \$800,000 joint Council-NEH grant to the University of Chicago for development and operational testing of a data management system at the library. [\$400,000 – 1970]	_____	_____
New England Board of Higher Education , to test the transferability of the Ohio College Library Center's computer-based bibliographic system to other libraries. [\$53,589 – 1972]	(4,086)	1,503
New England Board of Higher Education , for a technical and user audit of the New England Library Information Network (NELINET) cataloging-support subsystem. [\$24,000 – 1971]	_____	4,000
Ohio College Library Center (OCLC) , toward further development of OCLC's computerized regional system. [\$194,000 – 1973]	_____	85,000
Ohio State University Research Foundation , for a selective statistical study of transaction activity in a large on-line automated circulation system (Ohio State University Libraries).	4,146	4,146
Revision of the Handbook of Data Processing for Libraries (CLR-administered), to Becker and Hayes, Inc., royalties received from John Wiley & Sons, Inc., publisher of first edition, originally prepared under 1965 CLR grant to the Regents of the University of California.	9,645	9,645
Southeastern Library Network (SOLINET) , partial support of the program to train librarians to participate in the SOLINET system.	10,000	_____
Southwestern Library Association , toward further development of its six-state Southwestern Library Interstate Cooperative Endeavor (SLICE) program aimed at increasing and stimulating the sharing of library resources, services, and expertise within the region. [\$50,000 – 1973]	_____	11,600
Washington State Library , to support the further development of Washington State's computerized statewide network. [\$25,000 – 1973]	_____	5,000
AUTOMATION AND NETWORKS TOTALS, 1973-74	\$ 19,705	\$187,144

academic and research libraries

Academic and research libraries have always been the Council's particular concern. Their increasing costs [the median budget of the 81 university members of the Association of Research Libraries (ARL) in 1972-73 was \$3,026,243—up \$170,000 from 1971-72]²⁰ are matched only by the increasing problems and demands they face. Earlier this year in Chicago, Herman Fussler, Martin A. Ryerson Distinguished Service Professor at the University of Chicago, concluded a major presentation to ARL members with the gloomy forecast that economic conditions for libraries may worsen. He added, on a more hopeful note: "At the same time, it seems to me that we have the potential means, through the wise use of suitable technologies, new bibliographical systems, and the effective sharing of resources, for some very important, long-term constructive changes in our systems of access to recorded knowledge and information that could be of major significance for education, scholarship, and human understanding."²¹

The Council's efforts to assist libraries through projects intended to accomplish some of the goals Dr. Fussler has outlined are described throughout this report; academic libraries participate in and are affected by nearly all of them. This section is concerned primarily with the management and planning activities of academic and research libraries, including the development of undergraduate programs. Three new grants were made in 1973-74, twenty-four carried over from previous years, and one project was completed.

**Office of
University
Library
Management
Studies**

ARL's Office of University Library Management Studies, now in its fourth year, continues its efforts on behalf of large research libraries.²² A new activity instituted during 1973-74 was the Systems and Procedures Exchange Center (SPEC) to promote and facilitate the sharing of management techniques and expertise among academic and research libraries. The center's resources are developed by collecting from ARL

²⁰ Association of Research Libraries, *Academic Library Statistics 1972-1973* (Washington: Association of Research Libraries, 1973).

²¹ Herman H. Fussler, "Research Libraries and Technology: Some Forces for Change," *Association of Research Libraries Minutes of the Eighty-Third Meeting 1974*.

²² XVI:11; XVII:24-25.

members specified data and relevant documentation: policy statements, procedures manuals, committee reports, brochures, forms currently in use, etc. The material is analyzed by the staff and presented in SPEC kits, packages of illustrative materials representing the range of approaches to management issues. Each kit is supported and promoted by a *SPEC Flyer* which defines the issue, describes the various approaches to it, and indicates trends and problem areas. Kits have thus far been prepared on: (1) Goals and Objectives, (2) Organization Charts, (3) Personnel Operations, (4) Status of Librarians, (5) Affirmative Action Programs, (6) Staff Training and Development, (7) Performance Review, (8) Friends of the Library Organizations, (9) Personnel Classification Schemes and Job Descriptions, and (10) Collective Bargaining. SPEC services are available to non-ARL member libraries on a subscription or single purchase basis.

The Management and Review Analysis Program (MRAP) remains the office's major activity. Duane Webster, director of the office, summed up the experience gained to date in an article on MRAP appearing in the March 1974 *College and Research Libraries*: "[Our] experience suggests that there are certain conditions that facilitate constructive change. First, the motives for wanting change must be stated honestly and be generally understood and accepted by all involved. Second, the method used must be appropriate to the stage of development and special needs of the library. The third ingredient is the commitment to act. Change can and will happen, but, in order for libraries to influence this stream of events, intervention is required. The MRAP is a tool for those determined to act."²³

Recommended expansion of JUL

A Council grant to Fisk University on behalf of the Nashville University Center supported a study of the feasibility of extending membership in the Joint University Libraries (JUL)—composed of Vanderbilt University, Scarritt and George Peabody colleges—in Nashville, Tennessee, to Meharry Medical College and Fisk University. Prepared by Booz, Allen & Hamilton, Inc., the report included as one of its suggestions and recommendations that Fisk and Meharry—members of the Nashville University Center along with the JUL institutions—enter into a limited-term service contract with JUL which would provide them with full access to JUL materials. As soon as essential experiences can be gained under such a service agreement, the report went on to state, a further decision should be made regarding future relationships.

Planning, research at JUL, Columbia

The Columbia University Library Planning Office has completed the second and JUL's research and development unit the fifth year of activity since receiving their initial funding from the Council. At both

²³ Duane Webster, "The Management Review and Analysis Program," *College & Research Libraries* 35 (March 1974).

institutions the work is being carried out in a way that will make it possible for the results to be utilized by others as a model.

With the median staff of ARL university members at the 200-mark in 1973-74, Columbia's concern with organization of libraries and appropriate description of positions is readily appreciated. Its Planning Office is moving forward in these areas in a deliberate, continuous manner.²⁴

At the JUL research and development unit, activities this year included "a study to determine the feasibility of obtaining an access control system using magnetic machine-readable cards to monitor access to the various units of the JUL and also to provide time and attendance data for usage studies." This information is expected to have a significant impact on the method of budgeting in the JUL.²⁵

**Joint
CLR-NEH
College
Library
Program**

The Council's College Library Program, initiated four years ago in cooperation with the National Endowment for the Humanities, added two new grantees to the 15 institutions already engaged in projects to broaden the undergraduate library's role. As with previous College Library Program grants, Manhattanville College (New York) and Occidental College (California) will match the CLR-NEH funds for their five-year programs:

Manhattanville College intends to inaugurate a program of bibliographic instruction with student and faculty participation, building on an already developed introduction-to-college-resources program for entering students. The instruction will be provided by ten specially selected and trained student reference assistants. In addition to working with undergraduates, they will help department heads and faculty members in bibliographic updating. A full-time professional librarian, assisted by a faculty committee, will coordinate the program.

Occidental College, already supporting a strong general studies program, freshman seminars, and independent study projects, will add a "librarian at large" to its staff to coordinate a "faculty library consultants" program. These consultants will maintain fixed office hours in the library when they will be available to students and faculty colleagues. They will prepare surveys of library holdings in specific courses and in the curriculum generally. In the next five years each of approximately 15 faculty members, appointed from the humanities, will serve half time for one term as a library consultant under the program.

The previously funded projects are proceeding generally on schedule and are being monitored by Council staff and consultants.²⁶

**Selection
of books**

Book selection remains one of the major problems facing libraries, particularly college libraries. Later this year the second edition of *Books*

²⁴ XVI:10-11; XVII:25.

²⁵ XVI:11-12; XVII:25.

²⁶ XVI:12-13; XVII:26-27.

for *College Libraries* will be published by the American Library Association. The first edition was published in 1967, based on 1963 information. The new work presents a smaller selected list which will serve as a minimal "core collection," with individual entries amplified to provide more complete cataloging and classification information. Automated techniques have been used for the production of the list itself. This last aspect was accomplished by using machine-readable catalog records—regular MARC records issued by the Library of Congress, MARC records released by LC especially for use in producing the revised work, and records converted for this collection from older LC catalog information. The conversion list itself thus represents only one dimension of the potential uses of the data base which has been constructed. The Council has been active in planning, monitoring, and underwriting the overall project.²⁷

A list of CLR academic library projects active in 1973-74 follows:

	Grants and Contracts	
	Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
American Library Association , for development from machine-readable records of a 40,000-title book catalog as a core collection for college libraries. [\$290,502—1969; \$21,100 supplement—1973]	\$ _____	\$ 85,809
Association of Research Libraries (ARL) , toward support of ARL Office of University Library Management Studies for two additional years from Oct. 1, 1972 to Sept. 30, 1974. [\$130,000—1973]	_____	79,000
Association of Research Libraries (ARL) , toward support of ARL Office of University Library Management Studies for an additional year, from Oct. 1, 1974 to Sept. 30, 1975.	81,136	_____
Columbia University , for the Columbia University Library Planning Office. [\$126,308—1972]	_____	37,500
Fisk University , on behalf of the Nashville University Center, for a Booz, Allen & Hamilton, Inc. study of the feasibility of extending participation in the Joint University Libraries to Fisk University and Meharry Medical College.	17,908	17,908
Massachusetts Institute of Technology , continuation of the Project Intrex Model Engineering Library. [\$71,000—1972]	(4,771)	5,879
Michigan State University , for publication of a directory of university extension library services at member institutions of the National University Extension Association and the National Association of State Universities and Land Grant Colleges. [\$1,602—1971]	_____	_____

²⁷ XVI:14; XVII:27-28.

<p>National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH), matching funds to inaugurate and continue the CLR-NEH College Library Program, requiring matching funds from recipients. 1974 recipients: Manhattanville and Occidental colleges—\$50,000 each. 1970-73 recipients: Brown and Howard universities—\$100,000 each; University of Colorado—\$75,750; Davidson, Hampden-Sydney, Hampshire, Jackson State, Jamestown and Miles colleges, Dillard, Eastern Michigan, North Carolina Central and Washington and Lee universities, and the University of Richmond—\$50,000 each; Swarthmore College—\$40,000. [\$250,000—1969; \$200,000—1970; \$250,000—1972]</p>	<p>_____</p> <p>_____</p>	
<p>National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH), matching funds for a \$15,000 grant to State University of New York at Stony Brook in support of a faculty-student development team in history. [\$7,500—1970]</p>	<p>_____</p> <p>_____</p>	
<p>University of Lancaster (England), to support fundamental research on factors affecting the use of library service with the hope that appropriate findings will aid libraries to become more responsive to their constituencies [\$37,500—1972]</p>	<p>_____</p> <p>_____</p>	
<p>Vanderbilt University, in behalf of the Joint University Libraries of Nashville—Vanderbilt, George Peabody, and Scarritt—to establish a model research and development unit. [\$171,107—1969; \$89,475—1972]</p>	<p>_____</p> <p>_____</p>	<p>11,000</p>
<p>Wabash College, to increase the effectiveness of the college library by changing its concept from that of a storehouse of information to that of a workshop of the liberal arts. [\$50,000—1970]</p>	<p>_____</p> <p>_____</p>	<p>10,000</p>
<p>ACADEMIC LIBRARY TOTALS</p>	<p>\$ 94,273</p>	<p>\$247,096</p>

the public library

Public libraries in the United States spent over a billion dollars in 1972-73 in supplying services to their clientele.²⁸ In recent years the Council has provided support to specific programs intended to help the public library broaden its traditional role in the community – books-by-mail, independent study for college credit, research projects aimed at defining constituencies, and citizens information centers. Activities in all of these areas proceeded with Council assistance in 1973-74.

Library independent study programs

Traditionally Americans have pursued postsecondary school studies in colleges and universities of their choice. In recent years, however, potential students of all ages have expressed a growing interest in non-traditional learning situations – and, in many instances, in receiving college credit for such learning.

To encourage such independent study the Council, together with the National Endowment for the Humanities and the U. S. Office of Education, provided funds for the creation of an Office of Library Independent Study and Guidance Projects at the College Entrance Examination Board.²⁹ The office, now in its second year, provides a focal point for those public libraries already engaged in independent activities as well as those considering such services. A major contribution of the office this year has been the development of a series of promotional aids for use in newspapers and on radio and television by libraries locally in making the programs known to the public. The office continues also to serve as a national clearinghouse of information on libraries with independent study programs and to develop appropriate learning materials and study aids for their use.

Library information program

The Brooklyn Public Library Information Program is an ambitious plan to link the library's 55 branches to a computerized data bank, thus enabling them to provide available information about public services and programs on a personalized basis. Although the Council's grant was authorized several years ago, serious difficulties in funding from other sources have prevented full implementation.³⁰

²⁸ *The Bowker Annual of Library and Book Trade Information, 19th Edition, "Public Library Expenditures,"* (New York: R.R. Bowker Co., 1974).

²⁹ XVI:28; XVII:31-32.

³⁰ XVI:27-28; XVII:33.

**Los Angeles
Public
Library**

With the assistance of a Council grant, partly matched by the Educational Facilities Laboratories, the Los Angeles Public Library is completing a study of the needs, goals, motivations, and concerns of the people living in three diverse neighborhoods where branch libraries are to be constructed.³¹ The interviews have been completed, and the data now being coded and processed by the Opinion Research Center at the University of California, Los Angeles, will help determine the physical characteristics of the branches as well as the nature of the services they offer. The findings should be extremely helpful to city librarians throughout the country as they seek ways to make their services more appropriate and attractive to a changed clientele.

A list of CLR public library projects active in 1973-74 follows:

	Grants and Contracts	
	Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
Administration and Management Research Association of New York City, Inc. , toward the establishment of citizens' information centers in Brooklyn's 55 branch libraries. Council funds will be used for the salary of personnel responsible for creating and maintaining the central data base. [\$300,000 – 1972]	\$ _____	\$ _____
College Entrance Examination Board (CEEB) , two-year support of the newly established Office of Library Independent Study and Guidance Projects. [\$100,000 – 1973]	_____	62,500
College Entrance Examination Board (CEEB) , in support of the Office of Library Independent Study and Guidance Projects for a third year, from July 1, 1974, to June 30, 1975.	50,000	_____
Indiana State University , as partial funding of "Books by Mail Service" conference June 23, 1973, in Las Vegas, Nevada. [\$1,500 – 1973]	(337)	163
Los Angeles Public Library , Council's portion of \$48,320 grant made in cooperation with Educational Facilities Laboratories, to enable the library to identify needs, goals, motivations, and concerns of three city neighborhoods so that the branch programs and library buildings planned there can make the library a more vital part of community life. [\$32,200 – 1973]	_____	32,200
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , matching funds toward CLR-NEH \$50,000 grant to Dallas (Texas) Public Library , enabling library to investigate the effectiveness of the public library as a center for independent study toward achieving a two-year college education under CEEB's College Level Examination Program (CLEP). [\$25,000 – 1971]	_____	_____
PUBLIC LIBRARY TOTALS, 1973-74	\$ 49,663	\$ 94,863

³¹ XVII:32-33.

archives and special collections

The library collections and archives of learned societies and other special groups are often unique in their interest areas. Their usefulness goes well beyond the requirements of their memberships, for they fill important needs of scholars and researchers that cannot be met elsewhere. Their preservation and continuation is therefore essential to scholarship.

Various of the ongoing Council-supported projects in this broad area involve special collections in law and art, information on Russian regional archives, and archival aids such as the collection, care, and use of photographs and the care of manuscripts. A new grant this year centers on England's research libraries and their special collections. This year also saw the publication by the Stanford University Press of *Modern Chinese Society: An Analytical Bibliography* (three volumes), edited by C. William Skinner. The Council was one of many institutions supporting this complex project, which cost approximately \$780,000 as well as contributed time and services amounting to nearly \$300,000 more.³²

Private research libraries in England

A study of England's private research libraries is being conducted by Mrs. Valerie Bloomfield under the general direction of Sir Frank Francis, CLR consultant and director-emeritus of the British Museum. The need for a review of this kind had been felt in England and elsewhere for years, but until the Council decided to look into the matter no organized effort in recent years had been made to collect full particulars on these valuable collections and the institutions that house them.

The study will describe the administration and activities of the various libraries, identify their characteristic features in order to

³² XIV:32-33.

determine whether they fall into recognizable patterns, and consider the main problems that may be jeopardizing their future and the measures that have been taken to meet them. It is hoped that as a result it will be possible to judge whether any recommendations can be made regarding their future effectiveness.

**N.Y. State
government
information
needs**

A Council grant to the State University of New York on behalf of the New York State Library Commission for a study of its information needs is expected to produce an overall plan for providing library and information services to the state's executive agencies, legislature, and judiciary. The New York State Library is charged with providing adequate information services to an increasing number of state agencies and employees; yet, in addition to this major information resource there are over fifty separate agency information centers, several with substantial collections. There has been little planning and coordination of these resources.

The study will be carried out in four phases: (1) assembly of accurate data on existing state agency library and information resources in the Albany area, (2) identification and description of exemplary state government library and information service programs and patterns of administrative organization in some other selected states, (3) development of a plan for coordinating and improving library and information services to the New York State government, (4) implementation, on a pilot or experimental basis, of enhanced and expanded library and information services for state agencies. The CLR grant applies to the first three phases of the study.

**National
Archives
International
Seminar**

Nineteen senior-level professionals who are responsible for archives and/or record management functions in their countries participated in an International Seminar on Public Records Management held at the National Archives and Records Service (NARC) in Washington, D. C., March 17-30, 1974. Cosponsored by NARC and Unesco in cooperation with the International Council on Archives, the seminar introduced those present to the principles and techniques of modern records management adapted to the needs of the countries represented. A small Council grant made possible the attendance of several participants from developing nations.

In a report on the seminar, the National Archives and Records Service concluded that "although we may have more sophisticated information systems, and unquestionably a more fully developed Records Management Program, in the United States, we share some common problems with the developing countries. As an example, one representative wrote [in response to a questionnaire] that a major problem was 'the reluctance of various government departments to hand over their non-current records.' Another cited 'lack of trained personnel.' Both comments represent variations on a theme well-known to all records managers and archivists."

A list of CLR archives and special collections projects active in 1973-74 follows:

	Grants and Contracts	
	Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
American Association for State and Local History , for the preparation of a manual on the care of manuscript collections. [\$34,604 – 1970]	\$ _____	\$ 7,500
American Association for State and Local History , for the preparation of a book on the collection, care, and use of photographs. [\$10,000 – 1972]	_____	_____
American Association of Law Libraries , to conduct an annual statistical survey of law library resources in the United States and Canada. [\$20,000 – 1968]	_____	_____
Etta Arntzen , for a revision of the original 1959 edition of Mary W. Chamberlin's <i>Guide to Art Reference Books</i> . [\$8,000 – 1971]	_____	_____
Australian National Library , to assist in the travel of Asian librarians to the 28th International Congress of Orientalists in Canberra, Australia, and the publication of papers presented. [\$20,000 – 1971]	_____	(1,438)
Valerie Bloomfield (CLR-administered), for a study of significant private research libraries in England, particularly those in London.	10,000	1,895
Institute of United States Studies (London), for a preliminary survey of the market for an American studies bibliography. [\$5,000 – 1972]	(7)	593
International Association of Law Libraries (IALL) , to enable five law librarians from developing countries to attend the IALL's 5th International Course in Law Librarianship in Washington, D. C., November 11-15, 1974.	2,500	_____
National Archives and Records Service , as partial support of the International Seminar on Public Records Management held in Washington, D. C., on March 17-30, 1974.	1,814	1,814
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , matching funds toward \$10,000 combined CLR-NEH grant to The Social Science Research Council for a program to achieve bibliographic control of secondary literature relevant to modern Chinese society. [\$5,000 – 1970]	_____	_____
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , matching funds toward \$25,478 combined CLR-NEH grant to Patricia K. Grimsted for preparation of a book entitled "Regional Archives and Manuscript Repositories in the USSR: A Directory and Bibliography of Published Reference Aids." [\$12,739 – 1971]	_____	_____
University of the State of New York , toward a study of state government information needs.	25,000	_____
ARCHIVES, SPECIAL COLLECTIONS TOTALS, 1973-74	\$ 39,307	\$ 10,364

preservation and conservation

In his 1973 annual report, the Librarian of Congress qualified his positive view of "preservation and restoration of collections" activities with this observation: "One of the stumbling blocks in the preservation of many types of library materials has been a lack of fundamental knowledge about the causes and cures of paper deterioration."³³ This, of course, is a matter of concern to all libraries. Widespread interest in the problem was evidenced in the summer of 1974 when nearly 150 librarians and other members of the Rare Books and Manuscripts Section of the Association of College and Research Libraries met in Charlottesville, Virginia, for a conference entitled Special Collections: Their Preservation and Conservation. Keynote Speaker Herman W. Liebert, librarian emeritus of Yale University's Beinecke Rare Books Library, noted that technical problems are not the only ones requiring attention by the preservation/conservation-minded librarian. Equally important is the need to gain funds—at least one preservation cent for each acquisition dollar. Since prospective donors much prefer contributing to more visible acquisitions and development projects, these preservation cents are hard to come by.³⁴

The Council's awareness of these problems has resulted in its appropriating a significant portion of its budget each year for preservation and related activities. There were 12 projects active in this category during 1973-74—and several of the programs under the "microforms, reprography, and nonprint media" section which follows are closely related.

W. J. Barrow Laboratory

The Council's long-term support of the W.J. Barrow Research Laboratory in Richmond, Virginia, has been a particular boon to the world's librarians to whom the preservation of the collections is a continuing concern. The laboratory's most important contributions to date have been specifications for permanent and durable paper, determination of the causes of deterioration, and the Barrow one- and two-bath process for deacidifying paper.³⁵ Efforts in recent years have been con-

³³ *Annual Report of the Librarian of Congress for the Fiscal Year Ending June 30, 1973* (Washington: Government Printing Office, 1974).

³⁴ Jacob L. Chernofsky, "The Care of Books and Bookmen," *AB Bookman's Weekly* 54 (July 29, 1974).

³⁵ VII:20-23; XVII:37-38.

centrated on development of a morpholine vapor deacidification process for books in bulk. In order to insure that libraries would benefit from this new development at minimum expense to them, the Council has arranged patenting and licensing through the Research Corporation. Any royalties accruing to CLR and the Research Corporation from this process will be applied to further research.

Early in 1974 the Council assembled a group of chemists and library conservators to evaluate thoroughly the achievements and potential of the Barrow Laboratory. After several meetings and individual investigations, the counseling group agreed that the accomplishments of the laboratory were significant and recommended that its support be continued—ideally, planned and budgeted for two or more years into the future. The Council's board has approved further support for at least 18 months. It is hoped that additional funds can be found elsewhere for continuation of the laboratory beyond that time.

**Library
of Congress
Preservation
Office**

In making its 1969 grant to the Library of Congress for its Preservation Office, the Council expressed the hope that there would be cooperation between the Preservation Office and the Barrow Laboratory.³⁶ One such cooperative endeavor was the Preservation Office's evaluation of the Barrow morpholine process. In the discussions that followed, it was agreed that further testing and refinement of the process should be undertaken before determining whether to make it available commercially.

In its semiannual report appearing in the June 28 *Library of Congress Information Bulletin*, the Preservation Office noted that although much of its work load was routine in nature, significant progress had been made in several directions. Attention was called to "good progress in work on diethyl zinc as a gaseous deacidification agent for paper . . . [though] considerable work remains before the full effectiveness and feasibility of the procedure for the mass treatment of books can be demonstrated." Among other projects is an "investigation of brittleness in paper and of methods by which such paper can be restored to its original flexible condition."³⁷

**New England
Document
Conservation
Center**

The Council's two-year matching grant to the six-state New England Interstate Library Compact for establishment of the New England Document Conservation Center in North Andover, Massachusetts, has resulted in a facility serving its constituency at maximum capacity. The center's goals and achievements are being articulated effectively by its director/conservator, George M. Cunha, at meetings of librarians and conservators throughout the region.³⁸ At the request of a

³⁶ XVI:41-42; XVII:38.

³⁷ "Semiannual Report on Developments at the Library of Congress," *Library of Congress Information Bulletin* 33 (June 28, 1974).

³⁸ XVII:37.

number of cities and libraries, the center has performed surveys on the conditions of documentary materials and the environments in which they are kept and has made recommendations for corrective action. It has also carried out large-scale fumigations and emergency drying services for libraries in the region.

**Manual
on library
conservation**

The need for a well-written and authoritative book on conservation specifically directed toward the requirements of librarians has been recognized by the Council in its recent grant to Paul Banks, the highly respected conservator of the Newberry Library in Chicago. Mr. Banks, who has for several years taught a course on conservation of library materials at the University of Illinois Graduate Library School, is preparing a first draft of a manual based on this course. The Newberry Library allowed Mr. Banks six weeks of leave with half pay for the purpose; the CLR grant covered the balance of Mr. Banks' salary for the period and provided a small amount toward transcription costs.

**Related
publications**

Several publications and reports relating to preservation, conservation, and equipment testing have been completed during the year or are approaching completion. Included in this number are three supported in part by the Council:

Limp Vellum Bindings—Christopher Clarkson, head of the Library of Congress' Rare Books Restoration Section, has submitted to the Council a thorough report on European limp vellum bindings from Renaissance days to the present.³⁹ Packaged in a handsome wood cabinet made with hand tools, the report includes three volumes of text and photo plate descriptions, a large volume of mounted photographs, dozens of vellum samples, six reels of 8mm film, and a number of sample books demonstrating techniques appropriate for use with limp vellum bindings.

Restoration Techniques—Anthony Cains' workshop manual on restoration of printed books and parchment manuscripts, based on the practices of the Restoration Department of the Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale in Florence, Italy, has been completed except for the chapter on archival paper restoration techniques being prepared by Margaret Hey.⁴⁰

Library Technology Reports of the American Library Association on "Microfilm Rejuvenation: An Evaluation of Three Treatment Services," "Card Catalog Trays Made of Plastic with Wood Fronts," and "Card Catalog Cabinets—Gaylord Series 8000, Style V" have all been published following CLR-supported research.⁴¹

³⁹ XV:33-34.

⁴⁰ XVI:42.

⁴¹ XVII:38-39.

A list of CLR preservation and library technology projects active in 1973-74 follows:

	Grants and Contracts	
	Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
American Library Association , to evaluate the effectiveness of film rejuvenation treatments. [\$3,709 – 1972]	(\$491)	\$509
American Library Association , for performance testing of a new low-cost catalog card cabinet. [\$4,015 – 1972]	(224)	291
American Library Association , for performance testing of plastic card catalog trays with wood fronts. [\$10,219 – 1972]	(799)	201
American Library Association , toward preparation and issuance by the Library Technology Program of five publications that will constitute a comprehensive manual on the care and repair of books and other library materials. Owing to many difficulties, the program terminated after the publication of two titles, one of which went into a second edition. [\$30,000 – 1968]	(13,061)	500
Paul Banks , to assist in writing a manual on library conservation.	988	988
W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Inc. , for research on the causes of and cures for physical deterioration of library materials. [\$265,530 – 1971]	_____	52,454
W. J. Barrow Research Laboratory, Inc. , continued support of the laboratory's operation.	123,651	78,787
Anthony Cains , to complete a workshop manual on restoration of printed books and parchment manuscripts based on the practices of the restoration department of the Biblioteca Nazionale Centrale in Florence, Italy. [\$4,350 – 1972]	_____	_____
Margaret Hey , to investigate book and archival paper restoration techniques along scientific lines already under way in the Istituto di Patologia del Libro in Rome, Italy. [\$10,500 – 1972]	_____	275
Library of Congress , for assistance in equipping a preservation research office in the Library, extending the Library's preservation research in such areas as paper, adhesives, microfilm, magnetic tape, and motion picture film. [\$95,000 – 1970]	_____	_____
New England Interstate Library Compact , to assist that six-state consortium to establish the New England Document Conservation Center. [\$70,300 – 1973]	_____	32,250
Royal College of Art , (London), for a study by Christopher Clarkson of early limp vellum binding practices for purposes of conservation. [\$9,720 – 1970]	(777)	1,252
PRESERVATION AND TECHNOLOGY TOTALS, 1973-74	\$109,287	\$167,507

microforms, reprography, and nonprint media

The significance to libraries of microforms and other reprographic processes is evidenced in part by the broadening roles they are playing in the nation's libraries. Whether the librarian has turned to microforms for dollar or space economy reasons, for collection preservation, or as a logical extension of services to patrons, the fact remains that microforms of every description are beginning to compete in numbers with books and serials as an integral part of the library's collection. For example, the Association of Research Libraries' *Academic Library Statistics, 1972-73*, shows that the median collection of total microform units held by its 81 university library members jumped from 290,944 to 646,467 in the five-year period between 1967-68 and 1972-73. A decade ago, 1962-63, the microform unit collections were not even referred to in the annual statistical reports.⁴² As for microfilming for preservation, the Librarian of Congress's annual report of 1973 notes that at LC "more than 5.7 million pages [were] prepared for microfilming during the year. This is more than a 400-percent increase over 1968 figures."⁴³

During the earlier years of the Council, a not insignificant portion of its funding went for equipment development programs in this general area. Much of this effort had to do with adapting copying devices

⁴² Association of Research Libraries, *Academic Library Statistics 1972-1973* (Washington: Association of Research Libraries, 1973).

⁴³ *Annual Report of the Librarian of Congress for the Fiscal Year Ending June 30, 1973* (Washington: Government Printing Office, 1974).

and processes to the specialized requirements of libraries. This emphasis on copying equipment is better appreciated when one considers that: (a) so much of the work done in libraries by staff and patrons involves replication of collection materials or bibliographic information, and (b) the period of CLR's operation has been one during which various reprographic technologies have experienced very rapid development and broad application. The clearest evidence of this latter point has been the evolution of the office copier from a messy and troublesome contraption found in an occasional office to an essential piece of machinery in almost every type of institution.

While most of the Council's equipment development projects did not result in near term availability of the specific devices they envisioned, benefits in the form of a better understanding of the requirements of intended applications did accrue—and commercial development on occasion followed.

**Hazelrigg
camera**

Looking back to 1964, the Council that year made a small grant to Indiana University for the final development and testing by Dr. Hugh Hazelrigg of his cataloging camera with which entries from the National Union Catalog could be photographed onto three-by-five inch negatives for immediate printing of catalog cards using a high speed photographic process.⁴⁴ Two units of this inexpensive device were built initially and put into service at academic libraries in Indiana and Ohio. More recently a version of the Hazelrigg Camera has been produced by a Midwest firm and leased to a number of libraries under the name Copy Cat Library Cataloger's Camera.

**Mega
camera**

During the late sixties and early seventies there was an increasing awareness of the vulnerability of library card catalogs to both accidental and malicious damage. This and other less urgent causes led many librarians to make microfilm copies of their card catalogs, in most instances using rotary microfilm cameras because of the relatively low filming cost resulting from the speed of these cameras. Unfortunately, the quality of the film produced in this way leaves something to be desired, and the positioning of the card images on the film is not precise. Thus, if it should become necessary to reconstruct a card catalog from such a film by means of Xerox Copyflo, the cards would be of marginally acceptable print quality and would be quite expensive to produce because of the manual cutting operations required.

To surmount these problems, the Council in December 1971 contracted with Mega Systems, Inc., of Toronto, Canada, for production of a relatively high speed (about 100 cards per minute) catalog card camera, the film from which has precisely positioned, high resolution images.⁴⁵ The camera has been tested at the University of

⁴⁴ IX:27; X:40.

⁴⁵ XVI:42-43; XVII:35.

Toronto and the University of Southern California and is now being modified to eliminate problems discovered during testing. Meanwhile a modified version of the camera has been acquired by the United States Historical Document Institute and is being applied to the filming of large federal card catalogs. In addition, a large micropublishing firm has begun to market another version of the camera and is also expected to offer filming service to libraries.

**Monitor-
advocate
role**

The Council's long-term involvement in supporting the development of microform and reprography technology continues today largely through staff efforts in a consulting capacity and as an unofficial monitor of the industry for libraries. A Council staff member serves on the National Microfilm Association board where he has effectively represented the library community in this role.

A list of CLR microforms, reprography, and nonprint media projects active in 1973-74 follows:

	Grants and Contracts	
	Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
American Society for Information Science , partial support of videotaping sessions of the society's annual meeting held in Washington, D. C., October 23-26, 1972. [\$7,500 - 1973]	\$ _____	\$ 2,500
Governors State University , to assist its Learning Resources Center in a pilot project to develop, test, and evaluate an economical system for using selectively disseminated microfiche from the National Technical Information Service. [\$5,138 - 1973]	_____	1,400
Betty Jo Irvine , to prepare and edit a manual for librarians and curators, giving them background information and preferred techniques in the use of slides and slide projectors. [\$4,389 - 1971]	_____	_____
Mega System Design, Ltd. , for development of an automatic library card camera. [\$23,400 - 1972]	_____	5,850
Microfiche Reader Testing Device Project (CLR-administered), for the development of a booklet on reader selection and of a small set of microfiche to enable librarians to determine inexpensively and reliably the suitability of any microfiche reader for their purposes. [\$10,650 - 1973]	_____	2,559
MICROFORMS, REPROGRAPHY TOTALS, 1973-74	\$ _____	\$ 12,309

international cooperation

In terms of number of grants the Council devoted more attention to its international commitment in 1973-74 than to any other phase of its program. Nine new grants, together with nine existing projects and strong board and staff involvement in diverse international library activities, reflected the library community's increasing awareness of the importance of worldwide cooperation. The major portion of the Council's work in this area was with the International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA), now an important spokesman for libraries in international forums.

Continued support of IFLA Secretariat

At its September 1973 meeting at Grenoble, France, IFLA's president pointed out that the Council's 1971 grant for a general secretariat had made it possible for the organization to assume for the first time its full responsibilities as a major library force. With the establishment of the secretariat in The Hague, IFLA was able to initiate and carry out significant programs of library collaboration transcending national boundaries. The original three-year grant had been made with the expectation that a projected revised dues structure would enable IFLA to become self-supporting by the end of that time.⁴⁶ This was not completely accomplished, and CLR decided in the fall of 1973 to extend support of the IFLA secretariat for at least one additional year, through January 1975—not only because of unforeseen financial pressures on the organization caused by general inflationary trends but, more important, because of the quality of IFLA's performance in several broad and significant areas.

⁴⁶ XVI:37-38; XVII:40-41.

In no area has IFLA exercised more initiative and influence in recent years than in international cataloging. In 1971 the Council had made a second grant to IFLA, this one for a Cataloguing Secretariat, whose work since has resulted in a number of major breakthroughs in the cataloging field.⁴⁷ Its almost self-supporting publications program includes the well-accepted quarterly, *International Cataloguing*, and three important definitive works based on standards hammered out over a period of years by IFLA working groups: *Annotated Statement of Principles, ISBD(M)–International Standard Bibliographic Description for Monographic Publications*, and *ISBD(S)–International Standard Bibliographic Description for Serials*.

The activity of the Cataloguing Secretariat has made it possible for IFLA to begin work leading to a worldwide system for the organized exchange of bibliographic information—Universal Bibliographic Control (UBC). UBC has two major goals: to catalog each item only once, as near to the source as possible, and to make bibliographic information on all publications issued in all countries promptly available in an internationally accepted form.

A CLR grant of \$70,000—the major portion of needed support for one year—has been made to IFLA so that the expanded Cataloguing Secretariat (now the International Office for UBC) may begin work on the project. A new committee on universal bibliographic classification will include representatives of other organizations with similar objectives: Unesco, the International Standards Organization, the International Federation for Documentation, and the International Council of Scientific Unions-Abstracting Board.

At the September 1973 session of Unesco's International Advisory Committee on Documentation, Libraries, and Archives, UBC was singled out as one of the major recommendations put before the Unesco director general. The concept is also a major item on the agenda of the September 1974 Unesco Intergovernmental Conference on the Planning of National Documentation, Library and Archives Infrastructures. There is a good possibility that Unesco will provide partial funding for the UBC office on a continuing basis beginning in 1976.

Rutherford Rogers, Yale University librarian, is chairman of the UBC Steering Committee. Other members are Mrs. H. Anuar, national librarian of the Singapore National Library; Mrs. I. Bagrova, chief of information, Centre on Culture and Arts, Lenin State Library, Moscow; and F. G. Kaltwasser, director, Bayerische Staatsbibliothek, Munich.

“National and International Library Planning” is the theme for the IFLA General Council meeting to be held in Washington, D. C., November 16-23, 1974. A Council grant to IFLA has helped to fund a Washington secretariat to handle the arrangements for this first IFLA meeting to be held exclusively in the United States.⁴⁸

⁴⁷ XVI:38; XVII:41-42.

⁴⁸ XVII:42-43.

The theme for the meeting is the logical outgrowth of the work of IFLA's 1973 conference dealing with Universal Bibliographic Control. To achieve UBC, the concept of library and information services as a national responsibility must be accepted and planned for. Activities in this area are moving forward in some countries, but in many of the newer nations of the world nationally oriented library programs must be built from the ground up.

Other international organizations

The Council is also partially supporting two related meetings scheduled to be held in Washington at the time of the IFLA General Council meeting—the International Federation for Documentation Executive Committee meeting of November 18-20 and the International Association of Law Libraries' Fifth International Course in Law Librarianship, November 11-15. The Council's support makes possible the attendance at the latter meeting of five law librarians from developing countries.

Library services in support of international education

A Council grant to the American Council on Education (ACE) enabled its Task Force on Library and Information Resources of the Government/Academic International Education Interface Committee to hold an essential meeting with its advisors to discuss "Library Services in Support of International Education." Set up by Stephen A. McCarthy, executive director of the Association of Research Libraries, and coordinated by John H. Berthel of the Johns Hopkins University Library, the task force considered methods and means of providing adequate library and information services in support of international education in the 1970s and beyond.

A report based on this and other meetings and on Mr. Berthel's discussions with a special council of advisors and with personnel at several important libraries is scheduled to be published by ACE in the fall.

A list of CLR international cooperation projects active in 1973-74 follows:

	Grants and Contracts	
	Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
American Council on Education , travel funds to enable participants to attend a conference meeting to consider library and information problems specifically related to international education.	\$ 5,000	\$ 5,000
International Association of School Librarianship , toward support of the association's meeting in Singapore in July 1974.	1,850	1,850

International Federation for Documentation (FID) , toward support for the FID Executive Committee meeting in Washington, D. C., November 18-20, 1974.	1,680	_____
International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) , to enable IFLA to institute reforms and operate at an effective professional level during the three years required to complete restructuring of dues so that the organization may become self-supporting. [\$100,000 – 1971]	_____	23,367
International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) , continued support of IFLA's secretariat.	45,000	19,601
International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) , to establish a permanent secretariat for the IFLA Committee on Cataloguing as a center to promote and coordinate the international standardization of cataloging practices. [\$54,000 – 1971]	_____	16,800
International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) , to support the establishment of a worldwide system for the organized exchange of bibliographic information (Universal Bibliographic Control).	70,000	_____
International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) , travel funds to enable participants to attend two meetings of the Committee on Cataloguing's Working Group on Content Designators, held in Brussels in February and in Helsinki in May 1974.	3,500	3,500
International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA) , for support of a secretariat to plan and organize the November 1974 conference to be held in Washington, D. C. Additional funds were provided by other interested organizations. [\$10,000 – 1973]	_____	10,000
National Book Committee, Inc. , partial support of a conference on the role of library services and educational materials in educational programs in developing countries. [\$9,000 – 1973]	_____	_____
National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) , matching funds toward CLR-NEH \$15,376 grant to American Library Association Advisory Commission for Liaison with Japanese Libraries for partial support of second U.S.-Japan Conference on Libraries and Information Science in Higher Education. [\$7,688 – 1973]	_____	(412)
Dorothy Obi , sub-librarian I/C, University of Nigeria for travel to Dakar on February 25-27, 1974, to attend the landmark meetings for improving library education in Africa.	750	750
Travel Funds , to enable librarians and others whose work is important to libraries to attend appropriate meetings abroad at which they have a significant role to play. [\$5,000 – 1972]	3,000	2,447
Travel Funds , to enable important foreign librarians to visit the United States when their presence is essential for the purpose of carrying out selected tasks. [\$5,000 – 1970]	_____	1,835
INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION TOTALS	\$130,780	\$ 84,738

professional development

In the final analysis, the success of the programs, projects, and concepts discussed in the preceding sections of this report depends largely on the professionals who administer them. It is on their competence and creativity that the future of libraries rests. Although in a sense all of the Council's programs have been for the benefit of the profession, in recent years a more direct effort to assist has been made by allocating a portion of CLR funds for specific projects intended to provide help to librarians both as individuals and as a group. Two such programs have been in operation since 1968: the CLR Fellowship Program, characterized by many as one of the most important and beneficial undertakings the Council has ever supported, and the periodic academic library salary surveys and analyses previously mentioned in these reports.⁴⁹ Two additional career-development programs were launched this year: the CLR Academic Library Management Intern Program and a formal master's degree program at the Graduate Library School of the University of Chicago for individuals who have earned doctorates in other fields and are seriously interested in devoting their talents to library work.

Academic Library Management Intern Program

A fair amount of concern has surfaced among librarians and others interested in library problems about finding appropriate successors for the present directors of the country's prestigious academic and research libraries. Many of these people are approaching retirement; yet there appears not to exist within the ranks of the profession an adequate supply of potential replacements, individuals who combine the scholarly and administrative attributes needed to direct a great library. This year the Council's board of directors approved a program to select, on the basis of an open competition, up to five outstanding midcareer librarians of demonstrated administrative potential, each of whom would be assigned to work closely with the director of an academic library of acknowledged administrative excellence. Such a program, long available in business, government, and general academic administration, should contribute significantly to the pool of present and potential leadership so critically needed by our great academic and research libraries. After a rigorous screening process that included review by two separate groups and personal interviews for the ten top candidates, the following five librarians were selected:

Barbara Brown, head of reference and public services at Washington and Lee University, has been assigned to work with Page Ackerman at the University of California, Los Angeles.

⁴⁹ XV:17; XVI:45; XVII:48.

Ralph Edwards, assistant director of Western Michigan University's School of Librarianship, will spend the internship year at the University of Michigan under the supervision of Frederick Wagman.

Judy Fair, director of the Urban Institute Library in Washington, D. C., will be at Princeton University where William Dix is the university librarian.

Thomas J. Michalak, librarian for economics and political science at Indiana University, will serve his internship with Warren J. Haas, vice president and university librarian of Columbia University.

Barbara von Wahlde, associate director for technical processing at the University of West Florida, will receive her training at the University of Tennessee Library under the guidance of Richard Boss.

**Graduate
library
training
for Ph.D.s**

In 1973-74 the Council initiated an experimental program intended to broaden the reservoir of talent available to libraries. A number of research library directors had reported their need for and difficulty in locating highly qualified and intelligent individuals with the specialized knowledge that is gained through study for the doctorate in any of a variety of disciplines. This requirement appeared to be confirmed by the findings of Cameron and Heim in their salary surveys. In an attempt to assist in filling the need, the Council made a two-year grant to the University of Chicago Graduate Library School to be used for tuition and stipends for up to nine qualified individuals, selected by the school in accordance with their admissions policies. Recipients must successfully complete four consecutive quarters of course work to qualify for the master's degree in library science.

**Third
salary
survey**

In May 1974, the third CLR-sponsored survey of salaries in academic libraries by Donald F. Cameron, former head of the Rutgers University Library, and economist Peggy Heim, was published. As with its predecessors, *Librarians in Higher Education: Their Compensation Structures for the Academic Year 1972-73* was distributed to the nation's academic librarians and, through them, to academic administrators. The authors note the same "pronounced pyramidal structure" found in their earlier two surveys (1969-70 and 1970-71), a structure "with a handful of more or less well-paid librarians at the top and a wide base of very low-paid positions at the bottom."⁵⁰

Once again the study shows that professional librarians do poorly economically when compared to faculty members. "Fewer than 10 percent of the professional librarians are in positions in which the average compensation exceeds that of assistant professor in similar

⁵⁰ Donald Cameron and Peggy Heim, *Librarians in Higher Education: Their Compensation Structures for the Academic Year 1972-73* (Washington: Council on Library Resources, 1974).

institutions. . . . On the other hand, among faculty receiving tenure, probably 80 percent or more ultimately achieve the rank of associate professor and salaries commensurate with the rank." Cameron and Heim raise an interesting question in conclusion: "whether it is more appropriate to compare academic librarians with faculty or with general institutional administrators. . . . To an increasing extent both general institutional administration and academic libraries will have to solve many of the same problems. The problems relate specifically to basic occupational structures, to compensation levels, to career paths, and to psychological satisfaction derived from the job."⁵¹

**Sixth
class
of CLR
Fellows**

The Council's Fellowship Committee selected in April 1974 a remarkably diverse group of 25 librarians and other professionals serving the library community as its sixth class of CLR Fellows. These awards bring to 139 the number announced by the Council since the program was begun five years ago. Librarians working in 32 of the 50 states plus the District of Columbia, Canada, and Nigeria are among those comprising the six CLR Fellowship classes.⁵² Council commitments to the new class total approximately \$85,000. As in previous years, the individual fellows will receive funds for approved travel, supplies, and services from CLR and an appropriate leave of absence from their employers.

The 25 recipients of CLR Fellowships in 1974 and their projects are as follows:

John David Amend, library consultant, California State Library. Examination of selected state and provincial grant programs to public libraries in the United States and Canada.

Richard J. Beck, associate director of libraries, University of Idaho. A survey of innovations in space utilization, staff and user orientation, and book selection policies in western land-grant institution libraries during this period of continuing financial stringency.

Herbert Biblo, assistant librarian for reader services, Crerar Library, Chicago. To study the process of library unionization to determine if there is a set of common characteristics present in those libraries where the staff has opted for unionization.

Kenneth John Bierman, systems librarian, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University. To determine and analyze the current state of planning, research, and implementation for the replacement of the card catalog by some alternative computer-generated format for large collections.

Larry Earl Bone, assistant director of libraries for public services, Memphis Public Library and Information Center. To study the organization of some large public libraries and the management techniques used by their administrators, to examine the ways these large libraries relate to academic libraries in their communities and to larger library networks, and to observe the book selection and collection building processes in these libraries.

⁵¹ *ibid*

⁵² XII:35; XIII:41-42; XIV:44-46; XV:17-19; XVI:46-48; XVII:49-51.

Robert Keady Bruce, librarian, Carleton College. To identify, investigate, and evaluate the use of management techniques as applied to long-range planning in selected liberal arts college libraries.

Robert Whitehall Burns, Jr., librarian for research and development, Colorado State University. A comparative assessment of in-house operational statistics collected by automated circulation systems in medium to large college and university libraries over the U. S. and Canada.

John Donald Byrum, Jr., catalog librarian, Princeton University. To determine the current application of the Anglo-American Cataloging Rules by general research libraries as well as catalogers' suggestions for code improvement.

Susan Thach Dean, reference librarian, University of Wisconsin—Parkside, Kenosha. Three-month internship in the Rare Books, Special Collections, and Conservation Departments of the Newberry Library, Chicago.

Sue Fontaine, information officer, Tulsa (Okla.) City-County Library. To examine the state of the art of public relations in selected libraries in five geographic regions which employ three managerial patterns in the implementation of public relations and publicity.

Eileen Elizabeth Hitchingham, science librarian, Oakland University, Michigan. To investigate the use of terminal access to commercial on-line services for retrospective literature searching by college and university libraries as an adjunct to more traditional reference service: identification of user institutions, assessment of costs incurred, evaluation of effectiveness of such systems.

Herbert Frederick Johnson, librarian, Oberlin College. To study new ways of supervision—especially work group organization; to develop a plan for new supervisory concepts in Oberlin libraries; and to visit Scandinavian libraries, focusing on user-oriented programs and methodologies concerning work in developing effective needs diagnosis methods.

Anne Whaley LeClercq, nonprint librarian, University of Tennessee, Knoxville. To survey the purposes, facilities, collections and uses of nonprint departments in 20 university libraries to determine the current state of development and plans for the future.

Robert S. McGee, assistant systems development librarian, University of Chicago. To gather data on the history, status, and potential of computer-based library systems with on-line bibliographic files and to continue research and writing on the emergence of on-line library catalogs.

Jerold Arthur Nelson, assistant professor, School of Librarianship, University of Washington. To explore activities and attitudes of academic librarians concerning factors in interpersonal communication with the teaching faculty in order to suggest techniques for improved communication, to generalize about the status of librarian-faculty communication, and to derive implications for library education.

Harriet Keiko Rebuldela, head, Acquisitions Department, University of Colorado. To study the role of automatic acquisition plans in collection development-procurement in research libraries with book budgets between \$500,000 and \$1,000,000 and the extent to which commercially available, computer-based processing based on MARC has been utilized by these libraries.

Marion Taylor Reid, head, Order Department, Louisiana State University. To study the effect of budget adversity on acquisitions procedures in research libraries.

Harry Robinson, Jr., dean of learning resources, Alabama State University. To study library services to minority high-risk students in large universities.

Charles William Sargent, director, Health Sciences Information Center, and professor of health communications, Texas Tech University School of Medicine. To verify the trend and plot the growth of the greater responsibility being taken by libraries for their audiovisual holdings.

James S. Sokolowski, library systems manager, University of Massachusetts. To investigate how the National Serials Data Program might function in conjunction with existing and operational regional processing centers in building and maintaining a national serials data base.

Thomas Gregory Czetong Song, associate director of libraries and lecturer in philosophy, Bryn Mawr College. To study and develop plans for a new science library that will meet the requirements of a liberal arts college with extensive graduate curriculum.

Roderick G. Swartz, deputy director, National Commission on Libraries and Information Science, Washington, D. C. To conduct a comparative study of how West Germany, cognizant of library and information services as a national resource, is structuring its planning and development.

Herman Lavon Totten, associate dean and associate professor, College of Library Science, University of Kentucky. To survey and evaluate the minority programs in selected graduate library schools in the United States.

Rose Vainstein, professor, School of Library Science, University of Michigan. To visit five exemplary public library systems concerned with increasing staff and community participation in setting library goals with a view toward revising her instructional courses on the public library.

Larry N. Yarbrough, reference librarian, Northwestern University. To survey current and emerging performance appraisal practices among research libraries, identify and analyze those programs which represent the most significant improvements in these practices, report the results of the study, and suggest guidelines and requirements for improving performance appraisal programs.

A list of CLR professional development projects active in 1973-74 follows:

	Grants and Contracts	
	Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
Academic Library Management Intern Program (CLR-administered), to provide to four or five librarians with strong potential in administration of university libraries an opportunity for career development in 1974-75.	\$100,000	\$ 5,886
CLR Fellowship Program (CLR-administered), support for CLR Fellowships [\$64,950 - 1969; \$51,395 - 1970; \$47,565 - 1971; \$65,572 - 1972; \$81,430 - 1973]	61,319	66,175
University of Chicago Graduate Library School , for a program to support present holders of Ph.D. degree through the year of study leading to the M.A. degree in librarianship.	103,000	34,200
PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT TOTALS, 1973-74	\$264,319	\$106,261

**grants and contracts
payments totals
1973-74**

	Grants and Contracts	
	Approved (Reductions)	Payments (Refunds)
NATIONAL LIBRARY SERVICES	\$ 69,880	\$ 2,011
AUTOMATION AND NETWORKS	19,705	187,144
THE ACADEMIC LIBRARY	94,273	247,096
THE PUBLIC LIBRARY	49,663	94,863
ARCHIVES AND SPECIAL COLLECTIONS	39,307	10,364
INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION	130,780	84,738
MICROFORMS, REPROGRAPHY, NONPRINT MEDIA	_____	12,309
PRESERVATION AND LIBRARY TECHNOLOGY	109,287	167,507
PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT	264,319	106,261
	_____	_____
GRAND TOTALS	\$777,214	\$912,293

Opinion of Independent Accountants

August 12, 1974

To the Board of Directors of
Council on Library Resources, Inc.

In our opinion, the accompanying financial statements (Exhibits I-III) present fairly the assets, liabilities and fund balance of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. at June 30, 1974 and June 30, 1973, the expenses, income and changes in fund balance and the changes in cash and investments for the years then ended, in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles consistently applied. Our examinations of these statements were made in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards and accordingly included such tests of the accounting records and such other auditing procedures as we considered necessary in the circumstances, including at June 30, 1974 and 1973 confirmation of cash and securities owned by correspondence with the custodians.

PRICE WATERHOUSE & CO.

**Statement of Assets,
Liabilities and Fund Balance**

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

	June 30	
	1974	1973
ASSETS		
Cash	\$ 115,149	\$ 115,314
Investments		
Savings account	2,319	10,595
Certificates of deposit, at cost	1,700,000	800,000
Commercial promissory notes, at cost		200,000
Accrued interest	9,972	2,219
Accrued royalties (Note 4)	2,934	696
Grant receivable from The Ford Foundation (Note 2)		1,976,461
Other receivables	3,303	
Prepaid expenses and deposits	2,137	1,676
	<u>\$1,835,814</u>	<u>\$3,106,961</u>
LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE		
Grants and contracts payable	\$1,270,989	\$1,426,792
Fellowships payable	96,652	103,725
Accounts payable and accrued salaries, taxes and employee benefits	40,572	30,479
	<u>1,408,213</u>	<u>1,560,996</u>
Fund balance (Note 3)	427,601	1,545,965
	<u>\$1,835,814</u>	<u>\$3,106,961</u>

Statement of Expenses, Income and Changes in Fund Balance

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

	For the Year Ended June 30	
	1974	1973
EXPENSES		
Program		
Grants and contracts	\$ 790,103	\$ 736,850
Fellowships	81,331	103,745
Less: Adjustments resulting from excess allocations in grants and fellowships awarded	(122,019)	(34,619)
	<u>749,415</u>	<u>805,976</u>
Compensation and employee benefits	197,472	177,039
Consultants' fees and expenses	35,589	30,848
Travel	20,523	17,819
Printing and duplication	10,793	
Other	6,209	3,760
	<u>1,020,001</u>	<u>1,035,442</u>
Administrative		
Compensation and employee benefits	129,279	126,785
Rent (Note 5)	27,947	24,783
Professional services	4,871	10,019
Travel and meetings	10,073	14,802
Equipment rental and furniture	3,800	2,156
Printing and duplication	8,041	7,829
Office and other expense	24,620	16,862
	<u>208,631</u>	<u>203,236</u>
	<u>1,228,632</u>	<u>1,238,678</u>
INCOME FROM INVESTMENTS	104,689	36,462
INCOME FROM ROYALTIES (Note 4)	5,579	1,761
	<u>110,268</u>	<u>38,223</u>
EXCESS OF EXPENSES OVER INCOME	(1,118,364)	(1,200,455)
Fund balance, beginning of year	1,545,965	2,746,420
Fund balance, end of year (Note 3)	<u>\$ 427,601</u>	<u>\$ 1,545,965</u>

Statement of Changes in Cash and Investments

Council on Library Resources, Inc.

	For the Year Ended June 30	
	1974	1973
CASH RECEIPTS		
Receipts from The Ford Foundation	\$1,976,461	\$2,000,000
Income from investments and royalties	100,277	36,454
Grant and fellowship refunds	29,984	4,201
	<u>2,106,722</u>	<u>2,040,655</u>
CASH DISBURSEMENTS		
Program expense	1,208,883	1,198,014
Administrative expense	206,280	203,784
Other		50
	<u>1,415,163</u>	<u>1,401,848</u>
Increase	691,559	638,807
Increase in accrued interest	7,753	2,156
Cash and investments, beginning of year	1,128,128	487,165
Cash and investments, end of year	<u>\$1,827,440</u>	<u>\$1,128,128</u>

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

1. Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

The financial statements of the Council on Library Resources, Inc. are prepared on the accrual basis of accounting. Grants and fellowships are recorded as an expense when the applicable grant or fellowship agreement is entered into. Purchases of office furniture and equipment are recorded as an expense in the year acquired.

2. The Ford Foundation Grant

Effective July 1, 1974, The Ford Foundation has approved an additional \$6,000,000 grant to the Council for continuation of its program. The new grant agreement specifies that the grant is to be expended in substantial compliance with an annual budget of approximately \$2,000,000 for a three-year period beginning July 1, 1974.

3. Appropriation of Funds

At June 30, 1974 and June 30, 1973 \$1,106,441 and \$569,360, respectively, had been appropriated by the Board of Directors for specific grants and contracts. In addition, at those dates \$92,500 and \$95,000 respectively, had been allocated to the President for future grants and contracts up to \$25,000 or additions to existing grants and contracts of up to \$5,000 each to be made at his discretion. The excess of appropriated amounts over the Fund Balance at June 30, 1974, is attributable to appropriations made upon receipt of notification from The Ford Foundation of the grant which became effective July 1, 1974.

4. Royalties

The Council receives royalties from the sale of a publication entitled, "Handbook of Data Processing for Libraries" which was developed under its sponsorship. Such royalties are being used to fund the preparation of a revision and supplement to this work. The Council has also received royalties under an agreement relating to the publication and the sale of a book entitled, "Economics of Academic Libraries" which was developed under its sponsorship.

5. Commitments

The Council leases office space under a lease expiring November 30, 1977 providing for minimum annual rentals of approximately \$28,150.

Index to active CLR projects, 1973-74

In the fiscal year 1973-74 the Council on Library Resources made 29 new grants for projects and monitored 69 others which had been funded in earlier years. In reading the financial summaries which follow each section of the report, note that the first column of figures indicates grants approved in 1973-74; the second column, payments on new grants and on grants approved in earlier years. The original amounts and dates of the earlier authorizations not fully paid at the beginning of fiscal 1974 are given in brackets [] at the end of each entry. An index of institutional recipients and CLR-monitored projects cited in this report follows:

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Acknowledgements

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